

An Evaluation of the Problems and Prospects of Industrialization in the Rural and Urban Communities in Enugu

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Industrialization is one of the major sectors that can take Enugu State and Nigeria to an appreciable level of economic development and employment generation. The researcher aimed at evaluating the problems and prospects of industrialization in the rural and urban communities of Enugu State. Review of related literature were affected, proper identification of some important issues about Enugu State which is the study area were done in chapter three. The researcher adopted sample survey design and pilot survey. Sample sizes of four hundred (400) respondents were selected from the total population to represent Enugu State. The selection is based on areas where there are industrial potentials. The researcher adopted clustered sampling techniques which select areas of the zones that have similar characteristics to represent the entire zones in the state. The methods for data collection adopted are primary and secondary data collection. Tables, charts, maps and figures were used to present and analyze data. Some of the major problems of industrialization identified in the study area are: lack of infrastructural facilities, illiteracy, wrong perceptions towards industrial development, lack of raw materials, lack of credit or poor access to credit, locational problems and high cost of landed property or high value of land. The major prospects of industrialization identified are: infrastructural development, employment generation, growth and development of state economy, improvement in the living standard of people, stimulation of other sectors, and encouraging raw material provision. It is hoped that the problems of industrialization will be eradicated if the suggestions and recommendations outlined in this study will be implemented and there will be a new lease of life to the people of Enugu State and industrialists and this will improve the socio-economic standard of living, improve infrastructural development, eradicate unemployment and bring about physical and socio-economic development for Enugu State.

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Problems and Prospects of Industrialization; Rural and Urban Communities; Enugu State; Socio-Economic Standard of Living; Infrastructural Development

Introduction

One factor considered common to all countries which without it the country can hardly achieve rapid economic and social transformation is industrialization. By industrialization we mean, the process of building up a country or region's capacity to process raw materials and to manufacture goods for consumption or further production (Todaro, 1977; Okereke, 2000; Onwuka, 2005 and Udoh, 1990). Thus, a substantial increase in the share of manufacturing in total output is an indication that a country's economy has passed through the process of industrialization (Also see Ekpe, 2001; Essien, 2004 & Akpan, 2005).

It has been argued that, rapid industrialization either of a country or state is a variable instrument for economic development as it will propel economic growth and quickens the achievement of structural transformation and diversification of the economy. It has also been reasoned that industrialization of Nigeria economy will play a key role in rising of the people's standard of living through the utilization of full endowment thereby reducing the continent's dependency on the developed societies for its growth and sustenance (Dauda, 2004). Generally speaking, Nigeria's industrialization has been seen as a major area that can quickens economic development and enhances social progress. The need for Nigerian states to pursue aggressive industrialization is therefore necessary (Asante, 1995).

Some states in Nigeria, after attaining political independence, aimed at rapid industrialization. One of the major reasons for rapid industrialization has been the desire to break away from traditional colonial economic denomination of being not suppliers of raw materials to the imperialist states and net importers of manufactured goods from the advanced industrialized countries.

Also, it was observed that agriculture which has been the main source of Nigerian's economy has been deteriorating in its productivity. Agricultural products such as palm oil/kernel, cocoa, groundnut, coffee, cotton, rubber etcetera, have stray considerably, while its prices at the international market had collapsed drastically. Thus, contributing less than 20 percent to the Gross National Products (GNP). While it was observed that industrialization appeared the necessary way out of the economic problem that Nigerian states mostly Enugu state are facing, the role of agricultural sector however, could not be overemphasized, and for industrialization to create any meaningful impact in it was resolved that industrialization and agricultural development in Enugu State should, as far as possible proceed simultaneously since all Nigeria's economy is agricultural base and oil base (Anyanwu, 1997).

Therefore, industrialization is a process that happens in countries when they start to use machines to do work that was done by people. Industrialization changes the society as it happens during the industrialization of a country; people leave farming to take higher paid jobs in factories. Industrialization is a process where people adopt easier and cheaper way to make things using better technology; it becomes possible to produce more goods in a shorter amount of time. Industries are the most important aspect of the economy. Industries refer to the production of an economic goods or services with an economy; the processing of raw materials to finished goods and provision for services is done by industries (Okafor, 2005).

Industrialization in Enugu state has not performed creditably well and they have not played expected significant role in economic growth. They equally have not influenced apprentice training so as to accelerate employment and poverty alleviation in order to foster economic development. This problem has been a great concern to the government of Enugu state, citizens, operators, practitioners and organized private sectors. With the realization of the potentials of the industries, governments at different levels in Nigeria have put up a lot of support programs to promote and sustain their development but Enugu State own did not work out as a result of some factors yet to be identified. It has been shown that there is a high correlation between the degree of poverty, hunger, employment and economic wellbeing of the citizens of the countries and the degree of vibrancy of the respective country's industrial sector.

Statement of the Research Problem

Every society across the globe has its peculiar problems and challenges. Enugu state is not exceptional. As an old eastern state, the state is faced with social, political, economic and cultural problems, but the most problem is economical which has in one way affected the well-being of the populace. Such problem bedeviling the state is unemployment, which has serious implication for state development due to lack of industrial sectors in the state.

Lack of industrialization in Enugu State has a great factor in the high rate of unemployment and this unemployment is generally agreed to be symptoms of macroeconomic illness and economic cancer. Industrial sector and agricultural sector which were accommodating rural population in Enugu state have been losing ground to services. The share of industrial and agricultural sectors in the GDP has steadily decline from 36.4% in 1982-1983 to 18% in 2006/2007, unemployment is generally agreed to be symptoms of microeconomic illness which could be “voluntary” or “involuntary”. This situation has recently been compounded by the increasing unemployment of youths. Industrialization is the only means to ratify this problem of unemployment in the state because industrialization brings out several types of employment namely: wage employment, wage cum self-employment. Enugu state has continued to experience high rate of population growth. The population growth has produced overwhelming increase in youth population thereby resulting in an attendant increase in working size of the working age population without corresponding increase in the means of sustaining life and income generation. This population increase without responding increase in the means of sustaining has resulted to corruptions, vice, overutilization of infrastructural facilities, congestion in the state, environmental pollution traffic and transportation problems, indiscriminate disposal of waste, sewage and sullage, flooding etcetera. Therefore, in order to checkmate these issues, industrialization and industrial sector has to be improved and look upon to balance population increase with means of sustaining the state.

All these problems and more prompted the researcher to carry out research on the problem and prospect of industrialization in in the urban and rural centers of Enugu state.

Scope of the Study

The study emphasizes on the evaluation of the problems and prospects of industrialization in the rural and urban areas in Enugu state. The study area covers the three senatorial zones in Enugu state (Enugu North Enugu South and Enugu East).

The study will further spell out the problems associated with industrial development and production in Enugu North, Enugu South and Enugu East, their contribution to the economic development and employment generation in the state and the solutions to improve the growth and development of industrialization in Enugu state.

The Study Area

Enugu State is located in the South East of Nigeria, Enugu shares borders with Abia State and Imo State in the South, Ebonyi State to the East, Benue State to the North, Kogi State to the North east and Anambra State to the West.

Figure 1: Map of Enugu State showing the three Senatorial District

SOURCE: RESEARCHERS FIELD WORK , 2016.

Historical Background

The name of the state derives from its capital city, Enugu. The word “Enugu” (from Enu and Ugwu) means “top of the hill”. The first European settlers arrived in the area in 1909, led by a British mining engineer, Albert Kitson. In his quest for silver, he discovered coal in the Udi Ridge. Colonial Governor of Nigeria Frederick Lugard took keen interest in the discovery, and by 1914 the first shipment of coal was made to Britain. As mining activities increased in the area, a permanent cosmopolitan settlement emerged, supported by a railway system. Enugu acquired township status in 1917 and became strategic to British interests.

Historical Development

Enugu State was created on August 27, 1991 with the city of Enugu as its capital. The state derives its name from the capital city which was established in 1912 as a small coal mining town, but later grew to become the capital of the former Eastern Region of Nigeria (Ministry of Information, 1992). In 1967 when the Gowon administration created twelve states in Nigeria, Enugu remained the capital of the East Central State of Nigeria, one of the three states carved out of the former Eastern Region. Nine years later, two states, Anambra and Imo, were carved out of the East Central State and Enugu continued to serve as the capital of Anambra State. The administrative hinterland of the city became much smaller in 1991 when Anambra State was further split from Enugu State and the new Anambra State.

Population

Enugu State is made up of seventeen (17) Local Governments with two hundred and fourteen communities (214). Enugu State has a total population of four million, three hundred and forty-seven thousand three hundred and forty-eight people (4,347,348) in 2015, collected from National Population Commission (NPC); 1991 census community result harmonized for Enugu State. March 2015, this population is within a total area of 7,161km² (2,761.99sq mi). This value gives a population density of about 268 persons’ per sqkm. The population concentration of Enugu State

is high in the Enugu Urban centres which comprises three local government; Enugu East, Enugu North and Enugu South and Nsukka Urban Centre.

The population concentration of Enugu State is high in the Urban centres with density ranging between 300 and 600 per sq. km. This is predominantly in these cities of Enugu; Enugu Urban, Oji River, Nsukka, Agbani, Awgu, Udi and Obollo.

Table 1: Population of Enugu State

S/N	Name of local govt area.	No of Comm.	Male	Female	Both 1991	Both 2006	Both 2015	Ranking
1.	Awgu	20	62,859	73,766	136,625	197,292	270,307	8 th
2.	Aninri	5	42,890	52,730	95,620	136,221	180,871	15 th
3.	Enugu East	4	88,729	92,396	181,125	277,119	367,957	2 nd
4.	Enugu North	7	75,102	71,237	146,339	242,140	321,510	4 th
5.	Enugu South	8	66,907	70,143	137,050	198,032	262,943	7 th
6.	Ezeagu	22	52,254	60,500	112,754	170,603	226,617	10 th
7.	Igbo-Etiti	13	64,378	74,023	138,401	208,333	276,617	6 th
8.	Igbo-Eze North	19	62,671	76,619	139,290	258,829	343,664	3 rd
9.	Igbo-Eze South	11	34,350	41,291	75,641	147,364	195,664	14 th
10.	Isi-Uzo	5	38,981	46,765	85,746	148,597	197,304	12 th
11.	Nkanu East	16	52,332	62,143	114,475	153,591	203,990	11 th
12.	Nkanu West	13	47,210	55,719	102,929	147,385	195,685	13 th
13.	Nsukka South	15	103,939	116,472	220,411	309,448	410,877	1 st
14.	Oji River	7	40,152	46,209	86,361	128,741	170,942	16 th
15.	Udenu	9	51,758	59,891	111,649	178,687	237,256	9 th
16.	Udi	24	75,291	85,209	160,500	238,305	316,420	5 th
17.	Uzo-Uwani	16	41,993	46,119	88,112	127,150	168,821	17 th
Total	17 LGAS	214	1,552,116	1,718,719	2,1330,28	3,267,837	4,347,348	

Source: 1991 Census Community Result Harmonized with 2006 LGA

Industries

Industrial sector is one of the major area Enugu State is nagging behind, industrial sector is practice in a small scale and there are numerous problems that affects the fortunes of most of these industries in Enugu State. The slow rate of investment and development of small-scale industries and industrialization has motivated the researcher's interest.

Industrial and commercial growth had been sustained before a sudden change in the sector. Enugu State has industrial layout Estate at Emene, a sub-Urban community and Ukwani within the city. Emene harbours key industries which include ANAMMCO (a motor assemble plant for Mercedez Benz Trucks), EMNITE which manufactures building products, and Niger gas, producing industrial gas. There are also sunrise Flour Mills, The Niger Steel which produces Iron bars and other materials, and the Eastern Plastics Limited. The Ukwani is for the medium size enterprises. Industries on other part of the town includes vegetable oil product at nearby Achi, Livestock Feed mill at Ninth mile corner, Nigeria brewery also at Ninth mile corner, Ebonyi paints at Awkunanaw, Vanguard industries and the Nigeria Construction and Furniture Company (NCFC) which undertake construction and also produces furniture.

Some other industrial activities in Enugu State at Local level is the palm oil, wine and kernel processing activities at Uzo-Uwani, Igbo-Etiti, Igbo-Eze, North and South, Udi, Ezeagu and Nkanu. The gravel and sand extraction and quarry activities at Nenwe, Uzo-Uwani and some part of Aninri.

All these and more are the traditional industries prominent in Enugu State but are practice in a small-scale production due to lack of innovations mechanization, industrialization and financial problems.

Research Methodology

In the course of the study, field work was carried out which involves difference methods of collecting data. Some of the methods adopted are: Direct observation, oral interview, questionnaires and one on one interaction. Researcher's methodology employed was mainly field survey.

Research Design

Therefore, the research design adopted in this study is survey design. The two methods of survey design adopted is sample survey design and cross-sectional surveys.

Data Requirement

Data required for the study, were sourced from both primary and secondary sources. For proper evaluation of the study, the following data were used in carrying out this study. The map of the study area, the population size and characteristics of the study area, the existing industries in the study area both at local and urban areas, the infrastructural facilities available, the problems militating against their optimal functionality, and their contribution to the growth and development in Enugu State.

Table 2: Distribution of Questionnaire Sample Frame of the Study

S/N	Name of Sample Area	No of questionnaire
1.	Nsukka Community	50
2.	Nkanu West Communities	30
3.	Uzo-Uwani Communities/ Adani Omasi	30
4.	Udi	30
5.	Igbo-Etiti Communities	30
6	Emene Industrial Layout	40
7.	Enugu Urban	190
		400 Questionnaire

Methods of Data Presentation and Analysis

The information collected during field study was presented using tables, charts, plates, maps and percentage. While data got from questionnaire and interview will be discussed and analyze using histogram, percentage, tables and statistical test. The researcher adopted Anova Statistical test to test if the study is statistically significant or not. These are the methods the researcher adopted in both presentation and analysis of the study.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Industrial Spread in Enugu State

Information from the respondents, disclose that the spread of industries in Enugu State is very low. The researcher was able to identify ninety-one industries. These industries identified are both the registered and unregistered ones. It was observed that the industries are classified into three: the large, medium and small-scale industries. The information reveals that almost all the large and medium industries identified are located at the urban centres of the state, especially, Enugu East and Ngwo precisely Emene and 9th mile corner. This was as a result of industrial layout allocated there. Other areas where there are large and medium industries are at Nsukka and Enugu Urban metropolis. It was also observed that small and some medium industries identified are located at the rural areas of the state. The categories of industries identified in Enugu State are: Manufacturing Industries, processing industries, producing Industries, construction Industries, servicing and assembling industries. From the data collected, it shows that there are thirty-four (34) manufacturing Industries identified, thirty-one (31) producing, industries, ten (10) processing industries, six (6) servicing/Assembling industries and ten (10) construction industries identified. All these

identified industries are within the delineated area of study. These identified industries are summarized in Table 3 and 4 below.

Table 3: Classification of Industries Identified in Enugu State

S/N	Location	Large	Medium	Small	Total
1.	Nsukka	IIII	III	II	9
2.	Igbo-Etiti		I	III	4
3.	Uzo-Uwani	1		II	3
4.	Nkanu-West		III	III	6
5.	Enugu East	### ### ### ###	### ### ### II	###	40
6.	Enugu North	I	### ###	III	14
7.	Enugu South		I	IIII	5
8.	Udi	III	### II		10
	TOTAL	27	43	22	92

SOURCE: Researcher's Field Work, 2016.

Table 4: Types of Industries Identify in Enugu State

S/N	L.G.A.	Manufacturing Industry	Production Industry	Processing Industry	Construction Industry	Servicing/Assembling Industry	Total
1.	Nsukka	III	I	I	III	I	9
2.	Igbo –Etiti	I	II			I	4
3.	Uzo-Uwani			III			3
4.	Nkanu West		###	I	II	I	9
5.	Enugu East	### ### ### ### II	### ### III	I	II	I	39
6.	Enugu North	IIII	###-I	II	II		15
7.	Enugu South	II					2
8.	Udi	II	IIII	I	I	II	10
	Total	34	31	10	10	6	91

Source: Researcher's Field Work

Problems Militating Against Industrial Spread in Enugu State

Ninety (90) questionnaires were produced and administered to the industrial sectors of the state. Equal numbers of questionnaires were collected back and analyze. Some of the identified industrial problems are: site location/unavailability of site, high value of land in the state, high cost of land in the urban centers, wrong perception towards industrial development, ignorance/illiteracy towards industrial activities, lack of industrial feasibility study, lack of capital/capital accessibility, inadequate skilled man power, management, marketing infrastructural and societal problems, lack of raw materials, inadequate labour and power supply government policy, multiple taxation, high electricity tariff, high cost of fuel, lack of incentives and fluctuation of dollars. While major industrialization problems were summarized in table 5. These were the problems identified by the researcher through questionnaires as the problems militating against industrial spread in Enugu State.

Table 5: Major Industrialization Problem in Enugu State

S/N	Major Problems Militating Against Industrial Spread in Enugu State	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Locational and Unavailability of site	11	12.2
2.	High value and high cost of land	7	7.8
3.	Infrastructural problem	20	22.2
4.	Raw Materials /labour problems	14	15.6
5.	Lack of capital /Access to capital	13	14.4
6.	Wrong perception towards Industrial Development	6	6.7
7.	Illiteracy, ignorance and lack of feasibility study	4	4.4
8.	Managerial, marketing and societal problems	7	7.8
9.	Political instability and Government policies	5	5.6
10.	Inadequate skilled man power & High industrial tariff	3	3.3
		90	100%

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2016

From the table, it is obvious that the major problems militating against industrial spread in Enugu State are: Infrastructural problems, lack of raw materials and labour lack of capital and access to capital for industrial establishment, expansion, production and so on and locational or unavailability of site.

Prospects of Good Industrialization in Enugu

The prospects of good industrial spread in Enugu cannot be over emphasized. The information gathered reveals that not minding Enugu State has poor and stagnant industrial spread, those industrial sectors in Enugu State has contributed and will still contribute immensely in the followings:

Growth and development of state economy; employment generation; infrastructural development; improvement in state Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Balance of payment (BOP); improvement in the living standard of people; social services development; Man power, training; self-radiance of individuals; stimulating of other sectors e.g. the growth and development of industrial sectors will equally create a ready market for agricultural producers who supply raw materials; Boost the internal generation renew for the state; brings about growth in international trade and high level of investment; improvement in innovations, technologies, research and development of the state and finally makes the state on industrialized state no longer administrative state which Enugu is known as: The prospects of industrialization were properly analyzed as follows:

Table 6: Prospect of good industrialization in Enugu State

S/N	Policy Makers Contribution	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Growth and development of state economy	28	10.8%
2.	Employment generation	60	23.1%
3.	Improvement in the living standard of people	28	10.8%
4.	Infrastructural Development	40	15.4%
5.	Man power training	25	9.6%
6.	Improvement in state GDP and BOP	13	5.0%
7.	Encouraging innovations, technology and Research & Development	15	5.8%
8.	Improvement in state internal generation revenue	5	1.9%
9.	Stimulation of other sectors	14	5.4%
10.	Encouraging raw material provision	32	12.2%
	Total	90	100

Source: Researcher's Field Work, 2016

From the above table, it shows that industrial sectors in Enugu State have contributed immensely not minding their poor and stagnant development and spread in Enugu State. It can also be deduced that industries contribution

immensely in the growth and development, employment, improvement in the living standard of people and infrastructural development in Enugu State. A typical example is Emene was a timid area with trees and grasses everywhere but as soon as industries starts to spring up the area started developing and now is one of the most recognized centre in Enugu State and South Easter part of Nigeria so far industries is concern.

Table 7: Industrialization Contribution Assessment in Enugu State

S/N	Variables	Excellent	V. good	Good	Fair	Poor
1.	Growth and Development of Economy	Nil	10	56	124	70
2.	Employment generation	10	42	58	84	66
3.	Improvement in the living standard of people	14	32	64	88	62
4.	Infrastructural Development	15	25	42	106	72
5.	Man power training	Nil	5	6	167	82
6.	Improvement in state GDP & BOP	Nil	Nil	18	81	161
7.	Encouragement of Innovation Tech Research and Development	Nil	Nil	52	101	107
8.	Improvement in state Internal generation	Nil	8	42	152	58
9.	Stimulation of other sectors	13	17	32	100	98
10.	Encouraging Raw material provision	Nil	27	43	119	71
	Cumulative Weight	52	166	413	1,122	847

Source: Researcher’s Field Work, 2016

From the above table, it is obvious that fair parameter weighed highest in the contributions of industrialization in Enugu State. This implies that the variables of the contribution of industries in Enugu State are fair which means that there are fair contributions of industries to the following variables identified. Also, the second is poor which weighed 847, this implies that the assessment of the prospects of industries in Enugu State is poor while good parameter weighed 413 in the table. This implies that contribution of industries is very low in Enugu State. Therefore, more effort should be done in order to revitalize industries sectors in Enugu State in order to ensure efficient and effective prospects of industrialization in Enugu State. Also, state government has to device policies strategies, measures, and solutions to the aforementioned problems militating against. The optimum spread of industries in Enugu State in order to make the state an industrialize state.

Discussion of Findings

This sub-section examines the findings, that has emerged from the research carried out on the problems and prospects of industrialization in rural and urban areas of Enugu State. The findings are based on the reflection of the early stated aims and objective of the research work. The researcher was able to discover some important facts, which provide satisfactory answers as stated in the research questions. Therefore, the findings of the study are discussed under the following headings.

Disposition of Industries on Enugu State

From the information obtained, presented and analyzed, it was observed that the disposition of industries in Enugu State is very poor and slow. The researcher was able to identify industries in the delineated area of study. These industries identified are both registered and unregistered ones. The researcher also identify that these industries are of five types namely. Manufacturing, producing, processing, construction, servicing/Assembling industries, the researcher further discover that the disposition of industries in Enugu State concentrated mainly at the Urban Centres of the state precisely Enugu East (Emene Industrial Layout) and Udi (9th mile corner). The information reveals that this concentration is due to the existing industrial layout in the zones and agglomeration of industries to ensure economics of scale.

The researcher discovered that must rural centres in Enugu State have no industry and the existing ones are mostly small-scale industries, cottage industries, and micro industries.

The researcher discovered that the absence of industries in rural centres is as a result of lack of infrastructural facilities that will support industrial practices, wrong perception towards industrial development, lack of credit or access to credit, ignorance, and illiteracy of industrial development. It was discovered that some rural communities are so much bound by their tradition which their belief forbids certain development plans needed to be carried out in such areas. Also, the researcher discovered that out of the industries identified, 90% of it are located at the urban centres of the state.

Problems Militating Against Optimum Industrial Spread in Enugu State

Some of the tremendous problems militating against the optimum spread of industries in both rural and urban centres of the state as identified by the researcher were as follows:

Locational/Availability of Land

Locational and unavailability of land is one of the major problems that militate against industrial development in Enugu State, especially in the urban centres of the state. This is as a result of other land use activities competing for the limited land resources. This is the major reason why Enugu South Local Government Area of the state lacks industrial development.

Wrong Perception towards Industrial Development

Wrong perception of the community leaders, majors, and indigenes have impeded the development of industries in some areas of the state. Leaders, majors and indigenes have negative perceptions towards industrial development, some of the reasons are that industries bring about pollution, high cost of local products and material and over utilization of available infrastructural facilities. These issues have impeded the development of industries in some areas of the state.

Lack of credit/Access to Credit

This has remained the major constrain to industrialization in Enugu State. This problem is caused by the industrialists themselves, the government and financial institutions. Most industrialists in Enugu are unwillingly to share the ownership and control of their establishment with other investors so as to accumulate enough finance to run their business. This leaves most companies with little capital to run their businesses, hence, limiting their growth and development. Also, the stiff requirement and interest on loan of most lending institutions in Nigeria coupled with government negligence discourages industrialists from borrowing.

High value of Landed Property

High value of landed property is another issue identified by the researcher as one of the problems that retard the development and effective performances of industries in Enugu State. Some communities and persons valued their landed property so much that they cannot lease it, sell or dispose for any reason. Some places like Nsukka valued their landed property. This issue has resulted to inability of industrial to develop or get access for large land in industrial development, establishment, and expansion. This issue impedes the optimum disposition of industries.

Societal/Environmental and Economic Problems

Economic problem such as inability to generate initial capital or access initial capital to start up an industry. Environment such as topographic problem, soil type valley, impede establishment of industry. Societal in terms of marketing product most people in Enugu State prefer foreign product more than the local product thereby convincing people not to buy local product as they do. This brings societal problem for industries in Enugu State again societal problem as what to produce and efficiency of market. The orientation or perception of Enugu people on local product is very poor. This has necessitated to ineffective, unproductive development and performances of industries in the state.

Lack of Basic Infrastructure

Lack of basic infrastructure has always been obstacle to the growth and development of industrialization in Enugu State and even Nigeria at large. Enugu State lacks many facilities like good road, water, rail transport facilities, communication facilities and most importantly electricity supply. Some of the rural areas of the state lack these basic infrastructures such as iggah, Omasi in Uzo Uwani, also some places have epileptic power or insufficient voltage

which will help in industrial processes. These lacks of basic infrastructure hinders the progress of industrial sector or the establishment of industries and discourage potential industrialist.

Lack of Raw Materials

One to the poor state of our agricultural sector the amount spend on raw materials is high and the availability in large quantity is also a problem because manufacturing sectors find it difficult to get enough raw material to support massive industrial production. These make some industrialist to depend on foreign raw materials for their production and make those that depend on local raw material to be lazy, inefficient and unproductive in their production processes.

High Cost of Fuel

Most industrialists in Enugu State depends on fuel as the alternative source of power. Every industry use fuel either in production, processing, servicing and manufacturing activities. High Cost of fuel in Nigeria without alternative means of power affected and is still affecting industrialist in their industrial activities. Most of them complained bitterly that the cost of local production now is much higher than that of the foreign production. These affect the industries negatively in the marketing of their product

High Electricity Tariff and Multiple Taxation

Most small-scale industries collapse as a result of high electricity tariff and multiple taxation in Enugu State. The researcher verified that most industrialists cannot afford to meet up with the high price of fuel and they depend on electricity for their production which attracts high terrify for their production which attracts high tariff. Most industrialists in Emene complained bitterly about high electricity terrify and multiple taxation imposes on them by state government. All these are the issues verified by the researcher as the major problems that militate against the optimum disposition and development of industries in Enugu State.

Prospects of Good Industrial Spread in Enugu State

The data gathered reveals, not minding Enugu State has effects, and poor and stagnant industrial sector in Enugu had contribution and will still contributed immensely if properly harness to the following: Growth and development of state economy, employment generation, improvement in the living standard of people, infrastructural development /social service development, manpower training, self-reliance of individuals in the state, improvement in the BOP (Balance of payment), stimulation of other sectors example the growth of industrial sector will equally create a ready market for agricultural producers who supply raw materials, boost internal generating renew of the state, stimulation of the state GDP (Gross Domestic Product), improvement in innovation, technology, research and development for the state, brings about industrialization commercialization, agglomeration, modernization and finally, make the state an industrialized state and no longer administrative state which Enugu is known for.

Decision

Since the total calculated value of Y residual is 0.00 which signifies perfect correlation. This means that alternative hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, industrialization problems hamper the efficient performances and activities of industries significantly in Enugu State.

Finally, the researcher concord that if there are any industrialization problems as identified in table 6, that, it significantly affects the efficient and effective performances of industries in Enugu State and Nigeria at large.

Conclusion

Having identified the problems and prospect of industrialization in both rural and urban communities in Enugu State, I thereby conclude that, if these problems are properly handled, the writer is optimistic that, there will be a new lease of life to the people of Enugu State and industrialists and by so doing these will improve the socio-economic standard of people, improve in physical development, eradicate unemployment, bring about infrastructural development, encourages innovations inventory research and development in the state.

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